

Social Auditing and the Evaluation of Corporate Social Responsibility Accounting: Evidence from Selected Iraqi Companies

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Abstract

This study investigates the extent to which selected Iraqi companies are aware of social auditing and social responsibility accounting, aiming to highlight the importance of implementing these concepts in their operations. It also explores the role of internal auditors in identifying sources of environmental pollution and waste, and in promoting preventive strategies to mitigate such impacts. A structured questionnaire was developed and distributed to a targeted sample, with its reliability, validity, and credibility assessed using appropriate statistical tools.

The findings revealed several key insights, most notably that essential environmental resources such as water and air, which are consumed in the course of business activities, are not free commodities but shared societal assets. Therefore, companies have a responsibility to compensate the community for the depletion of these resources. Based on this, the study recommends that businesses adopt mechanisms for environmental stewardship and take proactive measures to minimise ecological harm resulting from their operations, recognising that these resources are collectively owned by society.

Keywords: *social auditing, accounting for social responsibility, internal auditing, social performance evaluation, business environment.*

JEL Classification codes: *M14, M42.*

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Introduction

The idea of social auditing is extremely old, It has existed alongside with human presence who was assigned to perform a specific work and then was held accountable for the result of performing this work. Despite this antiquity, social auditing as an auditing method is recent in accounting and auditing thought. There is no doubt that social responsibility has become extremely important in our current world, and its effective impact on companies and society as a whole is not hidden, as

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it is capable of bringing about a change in accounting thought if used effectively because it contributes to changing the lifestyle and environment and achieving well-being for members of society. Perhaps this issue is becoming more important in Iraq, due to the increasing the role of companies in boosting the country's economy which represents the necessity of following up on the performance of these companies and bringing their performance to the best possible level in a way that optimally fulfills the needs of society by employing competencies, resources and providing incentives. Most sources confirm that reaching an accurate, agreed-upon definition of the concept of social auditing and social responsibility and thus of the task of social responsibility is a difficult process. Corporate social responsibility is considered a center of attention in developed societies, especially in light of the intensification of competition between companies, the presence of consumer protection associations, labor unions, and government legislation that calls for companies assume their social responsibilities. Therefore, the report on the results of a company's social performance is considered one of the reports used to indicate the extent to which these companies fulfill their social responsibilities.

Research Problem

The relationship between social auditing and accounting for social responsibility is an influential and affected relationship and vice versa between the two, where the research problem can be summarized through two important aspects:

1. The research sample companies do not provide information about the social responsibilities placed on companies and related to the areas of human resources, structure, the local community, consumers of the product, through financial statements and analytical statements, as providing such social information will benefit and serve many beneficial parties, whether the government, creditors, lenders, customers, banks, et al.
2. The response of companies' management to the observations made by the external auditor related to their social responsibility.

By examining these two aspects, we find that modern developments cast a shadow on the duties of the external auditor and that this auditor should have an active role in diagnosing the role of companies in society and the extent to its response to the community service.

The Importance of Research

The importance of the research stems from the fact that it is one of the rare studies that draws attention to the relationship between strategic auditing and accounting for social responsibility and the mutual influences between them, in addition to the lack of writings on this aspect in the Arab world, the importance of the research lies in the following:

1. Defining the concept of social auditing, social responsibility, and accounting for social responsibility in business companies.
2. Paying attention to social responsibility by Iraqi companies will contribute to improving the level of well-being and reducing social and economic problems such as unemployment, poverty and environmental pollution.
3. The importance of the role of the internal auditor in demonstrating the effectiveness of the social responsibility of the business companies being audited, as the cost-benefit analysis approach is adopted to measure the level of activity of the research sample companies in achieving social responsibility requirements.

Research Objectives

By identifying the core research problem and underscoring its significance, the primary objective of this study is to explore and analyse the relationship between social auditing and social responsibility accounting, as well as their interrelated effects. In addition to the main aim, the study also seeks to achieve the following specific objectives:

1. To assess the level of awareness among the management of selected Iraqi companies regarding the concepts of social auditing and social responsibility accounting.
2. To illustrate the necessity for Iraqi companies to implement social responsibility accounting within their operational and reporting frameworks.
3. To shed light on the role of internal auditors in identifying sources of environmental pollution and waste, and in implementing preventive measures to mitigate these impacts.

Research Hypothesis

This study is grounded in the following primary hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant impact relationship between social auditing and accounting for social responsibility, which has implications for the various stakeholders who benefit from these practices.

Research Methodology

The research employed a **descriptive approach** to develop the theoretical framework, drawing upon relevant literature, including Arab and international academic theses, peer-reviewed journals, and reliable online sources.

In addition, the **analytical approach** was adopted for the practical aspect of the study, which involved conducting an empirical investigation on a selected sample of Iraqi companies.

The Conceptual Framework of Social Auditing

A Definitional Introduction to Social Auditing

The importance of accounting has recently increased. Therefore, financial accounting systems are supposed to produce useful information that is trusted by decision-makers from stakeholders in the institution. In this regard, interest in the reports submitted by the external auditor has increased (Abdulrahman, et al., 2024).

Social auditing is called by several names, there are those who call it personnel auditing, human resources management auditing, and social auditing which is the most commonly used. The difference in nomenclature is attributed by some to the multiplicity of terminology specific to the job, but others attribute it to the concepts and characteristics that distinguish social auditing from the rest of the auditing fields (Hussein & al-Shammmary, 2019).

It is also known that social auditing is an increasingly strategic focus for helping stakeholders to develop “best practices” for human resource management and social responsibility (Peretti, 2009).

Social auditing has also been defined as the process of examining an organization or the process of collecting evidence on a regular basis to evaluate the company’s social performance, represented by social programs and activities with the aim of ascertaining the adequacy and suitability of disclosure in social reports in expressing the organization’s commitment to implementing its social responsibilities, and the extent of the company’s actual performance of these responsibilities in light of approved and accepted standards, then reporting on the concerned parties to help them with decision making and policy formulation (Al-Hayek et al., 2015). Mohammed et al. (2021)

see the need to develop a comprehensive development plan for Iraq that includes all economic, social and political aspects.

From the above, the researcher defines social auditing as: that it is the systematic means of strategic diagnosis and drawing of the social situation of companies that is monitored by an independent person to reveal the strengths and Weakness in the form of imbalances and deviations compared to the basic references to improve the effectiveness of companies to adapt to the changes that occur.

Objectives of Social Auditing

The social audit at the company level, as a systematic means to improve the performance of human resources, to carry out a preventive and remedial study of current situations and achieve the following: (Salem, 2016).

- 1) Providing the necessary information about the social climate and work relations within the company and effective supervision, guidance and evaluation of the company's overall performance.
- 2) It allows the company's management to understand the behaviors of its individuals, measure their performance and the extent of its impact on its policies, and give the company a comprehensive idea of its level of performance and achievements through a general and comprehensive systematic report based on correct and clear data.
- 3) It allows the company to effectively supervise and direct performance, understand the relationship between the business and social aspects, and understand the costs and implications of the environmental, social and cultural impacts of its activity to choose among the priorities, modifying the application in light of the results obtained. It enables the company to report on its performance and social achievements in a way based on documented evidence rather than false claims.

Responsibilities of the Social Auditor

The responsibilities of the social auditor can be presented as follows (Shafaamri, 2014):

- 1) Ensure the company's compliance with environmental and social laws and legislation.
- 2) Providing information to management about the company's social and environmental practices so that the management can fulfilling its responsibility and making appropriate decisions.
- 3) Judging on whether the company has achieved added value from a social, environmental and cultural perspectives that was established to achieve.
- 4) Design a system to preserve the environment and protect it from damage caused by the company as a result carrying out its activity.
- 5) Evaluating the social practices followed by the company and working to develop them continuously.
- 6) Ensure that the decisions and social practices taken by the company are based on facts.
- 7) The auditor must take into account the laws and regulations when auditing financial statements, such as (Karam,2022):
 - a. Laws and regulations that impose obligations to compensate for environmental pollution resulting from past accidents.
 - b. Laws related to pollution control, emission reduction, or waste disposal.

Accounting for Social Responsibility

The Concept of Accounting for Social Responsibility

The concept of corporate environmental and social responsibility is a relatively recent development within the field of accounting. Numerous studies have examined how accounting systems have evolved in response to the environmental transformations faced by companies - transformations often driven by external events and contextual influences.

Some scholars argue that advancements in accounting theory and its practical applications have historically been closely linked to the company's environmental context in two primary ways. First, accounting systems have adapted in terms of recording and measurement techniques in response to environmental changes. Second, the processes of collecting and disseminating financial and non-financial information have been shaped by these environmental dynamics (Badawi, 2020).

Salama defined accounting for social responsibility as “an approach for measuring and communicating consequential information resulting from management's fulfillment of its social responsibility to the various beneficiary groups within society in a way that enables the social performance of companies to be evaluated” (Salama, 1999).

As for the definition of the Institute of Social and Ethical Accounting is that social and ethical accounting is concerned with knowledge about the company's impact on society, as well as about its relationship with all stakeholders who are all the groups that influence or are affected by the company's activities (Al-Faddagh, 2018).

The researcher believes that accounting for social responsibility can be defined as: an approach to measuring and communicating consequential information resulting from management's undertaking social responsibilities to various beneficiary groups within society in a way that enables the company's social performance to be evaluated.

Objectives of Accounting for Social Responsibility

The objectives of accounting for social responsibility are as follows (Abdel Aziz, 2016; Zakaria, 2015):

1. Defining and measuring the company's net social contribution: so that it does not only include elements of the company's private and internal costs and benefits, but rather includes elements of external (social) costs that have an impact on segments of society and this role follows from the shortcomings of traditional accounting in the field of measuring the social performance of business companies and this goal is related to the function of accounting measurement.
2. Disclosing the activities carried out by the company that have a social impact : such as education and health of workers, environmental pollution, resource consumption and this goal shows the necessity of providing appropriate data on the company's social performance, and the extent of its contribution to achieving social goals and this goal is linked to the accounting communication function.
3. Evaluating the company's social performance: by determining whether the company's strategy and objectives are consistent with social priorities on the one hand, and with the company's ambition to achieve a reasonable percentage of profits on the other hand and this goal is also linked to the accounting measurement function.
4. Providing information related to appropriate goals and policies for all members of society: this goal expresses the necessity of having a sound information system that expresses the company's goals.

Dimensions of Accounting for Social Responsibility

Some academic studies have identified the key dimensions of social responsibility accounting as follows:

1. *Economic Dimension:*

This aspect is grounded in the principles of competition and technological advancement. It encompasses a wide range of elements that fall within the scope of social responsibility, which must be addressed while maintaining fair and open competition. It also involves leveraging technological progress in a manner that does not harm society or the environment. The goal is to produce goods and services that are valuable to society at reasonable costs and with high quality. Within this framework, a company seeks to generate adequate profits while fairly rewarding the contributions of capital providers, employees, and other stakeholders (Rahmani, 2022).

2. *Social (Charitable) Dimension:*

Enterprises are expected to contribute to the overall welfare of the community in which they operate. This includes improving employee wellbeing through measures that enhance productivity, develop technical skills, and ensure professional stability, health services, and social support. The management style adopted by the company plays a significant role, as socially responsible governance positively influences human resources and community relations.

3. *Environmental Dimension:*

Businesses are responsible for minimising the negative environmental impacts of their operations and products. This involves reducing harmful emissions and waste, optimising the use of available resources for maximum efficiency, and avoiding practices that could compromise environmental sustainability for future generations.

4. *Legal Dimension:*

Companies are expected to comply fully with the legal frameworks and regulations of the societies in which they operate. This includes contributing to the resolution of social issues, protecting human rights, and refraining from all forms of discrimination based on gender, race, religion, or language (Ahmed et al., 2018).

5. *Religious Dimension:*

From a theological perspective, divine principles provide a moral framework for human behaviour. Humanity is seen as entrusted with stewardship of the Earth, accountable for its actions. Prophetic teachings are perceived as a means of ethical guidance and evaluation of human conduct based on divine standards, encouraging individuals to adhere to a righteous path (Sakak, 2021).

In conclusion, business organisations are expected to actively support societal wellbeing by enhancing environmental conditions and mitigating the adverse effects of their operations—particularly by reducing pollution and promoting sustainable development. Furthermore, prioritising employees' welfare by ensuring their psychological and social stability enhances their productivity and technical capabilities. Providing comprehensive health, social, and cultural support to employees and their families fosters a sense of loyalty, trust, and commitment toward the organisation.

Social Auditing as a Starting Point for Demonstrating the Effectiveness of Accounting for Social Responsibility

Many studies have shown that successful companies have realized that defining the responsibilities of the internal audit department in the field of financial reporting and compliance with legislation and legal systems is an approach that has become outdated. Therefore, these companies have

expanded the scope of internal audit to include the flow of social operations and provide consultations and suggestions for improvements in all operations in companies as means to increase the returns (Jonathan et al, 1999).

Saleh (2021) believes that developments in internal auditing are linked to various factors including economic, political, and social factors, focusing his study on social developments, considering that the auditing process is a social construction process that affects society and is affected by it. As for Al-Hayek et al. (2015) they see in this field that social work has a major and influential role in bringing about developments in internal auditing from the traditional level that is concerned with financial auditing to the modern level that is concerned with social auditing, and evaluating the efficiency of social performance has become a goal pursued by those interested in the matter of the company. The necessity of measuring performance and social activities in companies and preparing the necessary social reports was the incentive to find a way to evaluate that performance and examine those activities. Therefore, it can be said that the emergence of social auditing is considered a starting point for demonstrating the effectiveness of accounting for social responsibility.

Through the previous presentation of this topic, social auditing has become an urgent necessity because it is linked to the lives of individuals, as the general trend is to reduce the damage caused by companies and individuals have become sufficiently aware to know which companies are committed to environmental laws. Through social auditing, it is possible to know the intertwined relationships between companies and society and understand the cost of the environmental and social impacts of those companies.

Methodology

Data Collecting

In addition to a review of published studies and scholarly literature relevant to the topic, the empirical part of this research was conducted using a structured questionnaire. This instrument included items related to both social auditing and social accounting.

Population and Sample

The research community relates to a selected group of Iraqi companies in which we observed the use of social auditing and social accounting, through exploratory visits made by the researcher to many Iraqi companies as a first stage, and the second stage is the stage of distributing and collecting questionnaires to the selected companies, which consists of the following companies (Nokan Group Companies for Trading and Contracting, Newroz Group Companies for Trading and Contracting, Najm Al-Din Ready Concrete Company, Miran Group Companies for Trading and Contracting, Murt Furniture Company, Jarsteen company for Furniture Manufacturing , Sakar Group Companies for Contracting , Lana company for Limited Blocks) . The selected companies also took into account the need for their diversity in terms of the nature of the activity it practices as well as the sector to which it belongs. In a way that could lead to achieving the research objectives, it is noteworthy that the researcher distributed (35) questionnaires to the individuals surveyed in the companies, and (28) questionnaires were retrieved.

Testing the Credibility of the Data

The extent of internal consistency (credibility) in the study questionnaire was analyzed which shows the strength of the correlation or cohesion between the questionnaire paragraphs according to the following table:

Table 1. Testing the Credibility of the Research Tool

Questionnaire axes	Number of phrases	Consistency	Sincerity
The first axis	10	0.84	0.91
The second axis	10	0.85	0.92
The third axis	10	0.86	0.93
Total	30	0.94	0.96

Source: prepared by the authors

It is clear from the table above that there is reliability and validity in the study tool which reached a rate of about (96% and 94%) for all questionnaire questions respectively and for all questions of the first axis, a rate of about (91% and 84%) respectively, and also for all questions of the second axis a percentage of about (92% and 85%) respectively, and for all questions of the third axis, a percentage of about (93% and 86%) respectively. This means that the tool is characterized by a very high reliability and validity value as a whole and it is also in its details as shown in the table.

Descriptive Statistics

A) Descriptive statistics for demographic data

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for Demographic Data

Variables		Number	%
Gender	Male	21	75.0
	Female	7	25.0
	Total	28	100.0
Age	<30	9	32.1
	30_60	14	50.0
	>60	5	17.9
	Total	28	100.0
Scientific qualification	diploma F	8	28.6
	diploma A	4	14.3
	Bachelor	11	39.3
	Master	4	14.3
	Other	1	3.6
	Total	28	100.0
Scientific specialization	Management	7	25.0
	Accounting	8	28.6
	Banking	2	7.1
	Economy	6	21.4
	G. management	3	10.7
	Computer	1	3.6
	Other	1	3.6
	Total	28	100.0
Career type	Director	6	21.4
	Assist. Director	4	14.3
	Department Direct	7	25.0
	Part response	11	39.3
	Total	28	100.0
Years of service	<10	8	28.6
	10_30	16	57.1
	>30	4	14.3
	Total	28	100.0

From the table above, we found that the research sample with advanced degrees begins with a diploma and ends with a master's degree, in addition to the specialization required for the research sample where the largest sample is accountants and this sample is the intended sample because they have information about social auditing and social accounting.

B) Descriptive statistics for the first axis of the variable (social auditing)

As presented in Table 3 (Appendix 1), the analysis of arithmetic means, standard deviations, coefficients of variation, and relative importance for all items concerning the variable of *social auditing* reveals that the average mean score for this variable was 3.44, with a standard deviation of 0.56 and a coefficient of variation of 16.30%. This suggests that the general trend among respondents leans towards agreement regarding the importance of social auditing. Specifically, 51.8% of participants expressed agreement, 32.5% were uncertain, and 15.8% disagreed.

Among individual items, paragraph (X8) recorded the highest mean value of 3.57—well above the hypothesised mean of 3—indicating a strong level of agreement. The associated standard deviation was 0.68, and the coefficient of variation was 18.97%. For this item, 60.8% of respondents agreed, 32.1% were uncertain, and 7.1% disagreed.

Paragraph (X4) followed closely, with a mean score of 3.55, also exceeding the hypothesised average. It showed a standard deviation of 0.63 and a coefficient of variation of 17.70%. Agreement was expressed by 60.7% of respondents, 32.1% were unsure, and 7.2% disagreed. A similar pattern was observed across other items in this section, where the statistical indicators consistently supported the significance of social auditing in the eyes of respondents.

C) Descriptive statistics for the second axis of the variable (Accounting for Social Responsibility)

Table 4 (Appendix 1) summarises the responses related to the *social accounting* variable. The overall arithmetic mean was 3.57, with a standard deviation of 0.57 and a coefficient of variation of 15.98%. This again points to a general consensus among respondents regarding the importance of social accounting. Specifically, 57.1% of participants agreed, 28.2% remained uncertain, and 14.7% disagreed.

At the item level, paragraph (X1) recorded the highest arithmetic mean of 4.29, indicating strong agreement relative to the hypothesised mean of 3. The standard deviation was 0.75 and the coefficient of variation was 17.48%. Among the respondents, 89.3% agreed, 7.1% were uncertain, and only 3.6% disagreed.

Paragraph (X2) followed with a mean score of 4.04, also surpassing the hypothesised threshold. The standard deviation was 0.73, and the coefficient of variation was 18.11%. Agreement was expressed by 82.1% of participants, 14.3% were unsure, and 3.6% disagreed. Similar trends were observed across other items in this variable, with consistently high mean scores, modest standard deviations, and low coefficients of variation, reinforcing the perception of social accounting as a vital business function.

D) Descriptive statistics for the third axis of the variable (benefit from social services and the need for its services based on social responsibility)

Table 5 (Appendix 1) presents the arithmetic means, standard deviations, coefficients of variation, and relative importance for items relating to the third axis: *the perceived benefit of social audit services and the necessity of these services in the context of social responsibility*. The general mean score for this variable was 3.30, with a standard deviation of 0.60 and a coefficient of variation of 17.46%. These values suggest an overall tendency toward agreement among respondents. The arithmetic mean exceeds the hypothesised benchmark of 3.0, indicating that respondents recognised the importance of

social audit services in enhancing social responsibility. Specifically, 46.8% of the sample agreed with the statements presented, 31.1% were undecided, and 22.1% disagreed.

At the item level, paragraph (X2) recorded the highest arithmetic mean of 3.75, reflecting strong agreement with the item. The standard deviation was 0.91, and the coefficient of variation was 24.30%. Among the respondents, 64.3% agreed, 25.0% were unsure, and 10.7% disagreed.

Paragraph (X5) followed with an arithmetic mean of 3.54, also exceeding the hypothesised mean. It had a standard deviation of 0.82 and a coefficient of variation of 23.28%. In this case, 53.6% of respondents agreed, 35.7% were uncertain, and 10.7% disagreed. The remaining items followed a similar pattern, and in most cases, consistency was observed in both standard deviation and coefficient of variation values, reflecting a shared perception across responses.

These results from the field study confirm that the surveyed companies acknowledge the significance of social auditing and are responsive to the expectations associated with corporate social responsibility.

Table 6. Results of Regression Analysis of the Social Audit Variable on Social Accounting and the Entities that Benefit from Social Auditing and Social Accounting

Variable	R ²	Test t		Test f		Beta parameter
		Computed	Moral level	Computed	Moral level	
Social audit	0.81	10.34	0.000	107.21	0.000	0.886
Entities that benefit from social auditing and social accounting	0.31	3.38	0.002	11.44	0.002	0.681

The results of the statistical analysis showed that there was a statistically significant effect between social auditing and social accounting from table No. (6), with a coefficient of determination (R²) of (0.81) and the significance of this effect is confirmed by the calculated (F) value of (107.21), and the (p_value) for this test is equal to (0.000), which is smaller than the statistical significance value it also showed that there is a statistically significant effect between social auditing and the entities that benefit from social auditing and social accounting, with a coefficient of determination (R²) of (0.31), and the significance of this effect is confirmed by the value (F) calculated value reached (11.44) and the (p-value) for this test is equal to (0.002), which is smaller than the statistical significance value which confirms the acceptance of the main hypothesis, which states (there is a statistically significant influence relationship between social auditing and accounting for social responsibility, and this relationship has implications for the entities that benefit from social auditing and social accounting).

The test (t) is used to evaluate the significance of the impact of social auditing on social accounting, and we can compare the value of the moral level (P-value) with the value of statistical significance, we note that the value of (t) calculated for the aforementioned variable is equal to (10.35), and at the moral level (0.000), and this this means that there is a significant effect of the variable social auditing on accounting for social responsibility, and the degree of influence of the aforementioned variable is (0.886), since the more social auditing increases by one hundred percent, the greater social accounting increases by (%88). Likewise, test (t) is used to evaluate the moral impact of social auditing on the entities that benefit from social auditing and social accounting, the value of the moral level (P-value) can be compared with the value of statistical significance, we notice that the value of (t) calculated for the aforementioned variable is equal to (3.38), and at a moral level of (0.002), which means there is a moral impact of the variable social auditing on the entities that benefit from social auditing and social accounting, and the degree of influence of the

aforementioned variable is (0.681), as the more social auditing increases by a percentage of hundred percent the more the entities benefiting from social auditing and social accounting increase by (%68).

Conclusions

Based on the findings derived from the analysis of the study variables and in addition to those discussed throughout the research, the following key conclusions were drawn:

1. Social auditing plays a pivotal role in promoting administrative rationalisation and aligning corporate leadership with strategic objectives.
2. Auditors are required to consider applicable environmental laws and regulations when examining financial statements, especially those involving obligations related to past environmental incidents, pollution control, emission reduction, and waste management.
3. Accounting for social responsibility reflects the company's commitment to the community in which it operates, with such obligations expanding in accordance with the diversity and interests of stakeholders.
4. The economic resources utilised by a company, including those often perceived as free (e.g., water and air), are in fact societal and economic assets, for which the company holds an obligation to compensate the community.
5. The companies within the research sample actively contribute to societal well-being by fostering a safer environment, reducing pollution, and pursuing goals of sustainable economic development.

Recommendations

In light of the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Ensure regular oversight by auditors of environmental agency guidelines and monitor company compliance, including comparison of certifications awarded by competent authorities.
2. Implement internal systems focused on environmental preservation and mitigating ecological damage caused by company operations.
3. Enforce accountability measures requiring companies to compensate society for depleted natural resources, recognising that these assets belong to the community at large.
4. Promote preventive financial investment in environmental health by authorising accounting departments to allocate funds for environmental safety measures before pollution occurs, rather than responding reactively. These investments should be reviewed and evaluated in subsequent cycles for effectiveness.
5. Establish governmental oversight committees tasked with ensuring company compliance with environmental laws and standards issued by relevant authorities, thereby minimising ecological risks.

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Appendix 1

Table 3. Arithmetic Means, Standard Deviations, and Coefficient of Variation of Axis Paragraph (Social Auditing)

axis	Strongly disagree	disagree	natural	agree	Strongly disagree	average	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Relative significance
	number	number	number	number	Number				
	%	%	%	%	%				
1	0.00	5.00	12.00	9.00	2.00	3.29	0.84	25.54	65.71
	0.0	17.9	42.9	32.1	7.1				
2	0.00	4.00	11.00	9.00	4.00	3.46	0.91	26.14	69.29
	0.0	14.3	39.3	32.1	14.3				
3	0.00	3.00	11.00	10.00	4.00	3.54	0.87	24.47	70.71
	0.0	10.7	39.3	35.7	14.3				
4	0.00	2.00	9.00	17.00	0.00	53.5	0.63	17.70	70.71
	0.0	7.2	32.1	60.7	0.0				
5	0.00	7.00	8.00	10.00	3.00	3.32	0.97	29.07	66.43
	0.0	25.0	28.6	35.7	10.7				
6	0.00	4.00	9.00	14.00	1.00	3.43	0.78	22.63	68.57
	0.0	14.3	32.1	50.0	3.6				
7	0.00	5.00	9.00	11.00	3.00	3.43	0.90	26.35	68.57
	0.0	17.9	32.1	39.3	10.7				
8	0.00	2.00	9.00	16.00	1.00	3.57	0.68	18.97	71.43
	0.0	7.1	32.1	57.2	3.6				
9	0.00	9.00	4.00	14.00	1.00	3.25	0.95	29.22	65.00

	0.0	32.1	14.3	50.0	3.6				
10	1.00	2.00	9.00	13.00	3.00	3.54	0.91	25.61	70.71
	3.6	7.1	32.1	46.4	10.7				
Total	1.0	43.0	91.0	123.0	22.0	3.44	0.56	16.30	68.71
	0.4	15.4	32.5	43.9	7.9				

Table 4. Arithmetic Means, Standard Deviations, and Coefficient of Variation for Axis Paragraphs (Social accounting)

paragraphs	Strongly disagree	disagree	natural	agree	Strongly agree	average	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Relative significance
	number	number	number	number	number				
	%	%	%	%	%				
1	0.00	1.00	2.00	13.00	12.00	4.29	0.75	17.48	85.71
	0.0	3.6	7.1	46.4	42.9				
2	0.00	1.00	4.00	16.00	7.00	4.04	0.73	18.11	80.71
	0.0	3.6	14.3	57.1	25.0				
3	0.00	5.00	9.00	12.00	2.00	3.39	0.86	25.33	67.86
	0.0	17.9	32.1	42.9	7.1				
4	0.00	7.00	6.00	12.00	3.00	3.39	0.98	28.77	67.86
	0.0	25.0	21.4	42.9	10.7				
5	1.00	5.00	10.00	4.00	8.00	3.46	1.18	34.05	69.29
	3.6	17.9	35.7	14.3	28.6				
6	0.00	2.00	7.00	17.00	2.00	3.68	0.71	19.30	73.57
	0.0	7.1	25.0	60.7	7.1				
7	0.00	5.00	8.00	11.00	4.00	3.50	0.94	27.00	70.00

	0.0	17.9	28.6	39.3	14.3				
8	0.00	6.00	9.00	12.00	1.00	3.29	0.84	25.54	65.71
	0.0	21.4	32.1	42.9	3.6				
9	0.00	3.00	13.00	11.00	1.00	3.36	0.72	21.38	67.14
	0.0	10.7	46.4	39.3	3.6				
10	0.00	5.00	11.00	11.00	1.00	3.29	0.80	24.21	65.71
	0.0	17.9	39.3	39.3	3.6				
Total	1.0	40.0	79.0	119.0	41.0	3.57	0.57	15.98	71.36
	0.4	14.3	28.2	42.5	14.6				

Table 5. Arithmetic Means, Standard Deviations, and Coefficient of Variation for the Items on the Benefit Axis of Social Audit Services and the Need for Its Services on Social Responsibility

paragraphs	Strongly disagree	disagree	natural	agree	Strongly agree	average	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Relative significance
	number	number	number	number	number				
	%	%	%	%	%				
1	0.00	4.00	9.00	13.00	2.00	3.46	0.82	23.76	69.29
	0.0	14.3	32.1	46.4	7.1				
2	0.00	3.00	7.00	12.00	6.00	3.75	0.91	24.30	75.00
	0.0	10.7	25.0	42.9	21.4				
3	0.00	8.00	9.00	9.00	2.00	3.18	0.93	29.19	63.57
	0.0	28.6	32.1	32.1	7.1				
4	0.00	7.00	12.00	7.00	2.00	3.14	0.87	27.84	62.86
	0.0	25.0	42.9	25.0	7.1				

5	0.00	3.00	10.00	12.00	3.00	3.54	0.82	23.28	70.71
	0.0	10.7	35.7	42.9	10.7				
6	2.00	8.00	8.00	7.00	3.00	3.04	1.12	36.81	60.71
	7.1	28.6	28.6	25.0	10.7				
7	0.00	6.00	9.00	12.00	1.00	3.29	0.84	25.54	65.71
	0.0	21.4	32.1	42.9	3.6				
8	2.00	9.00	9.00	8.00	0.00	2.82	0.93	32.89	56.43
	7.1	32.1	32.1	28.6	0.0				
9	0.00	4.00	10.00	14.00	0.00	3.36	0.72	21.38	67.14
	0.0	14.3	35.7	50.0	0.0				
10	0.00	6.00	4.00	17.00	1.00	3.46	0.87	24.98	69.29
	0.0	21.4	14.3	60.7	3.6				
Total	4.0	58.0	87.0	111.0	20.0	3.30	0.60	17.46	66.07
	1.4	20.7	31.1	39.6	7.1				

